

RESILIENT BEGINNINGS:
EMPOWERING ADULTS THROUGH TRAUMA-INFORMED RESOURCES,
AN ARTIST'S CONTRIBUTION

By

Scarlett L. Rodgers

ORCID ID:0009-0009-7395-2890

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.11522523

A Project Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the
Requirements to Graduate with University Honors

The University Honors Program
California State University, Fullerton
May 2024

Approved By:

Date:

Dr. Melanie Mallers, Department of Human Service

5/6/2024

Dr. Stacy Mallicoat, Director, University Honors Program.

5/24/2024

Table of Contents

Acknowledgement	3
Abstract	4
Introduction	5
Project Aim	6
Literature Review	7
ACEs Study	
Neuroscience Connection	
Building Resilience	
NI2C's Values	
Logo Design and Themes	16
Illustrations	19
The Completed Workbook	21
Reflection: The Fulfilling Journey of Contributing to Resilience	24
Conclusion	25
References	26

Acknowledgement

This section is dedicated to expressing my deepest gratitude to those who contributed to this project. I want to give a genuine, heartfelt thank you to my mentor, Dr. Mallers, whose helped me realize the project possibilities with my ACE's research. Her support and guidance has been influential in finalizing this project. Dr. Mallers provided invaluable insights into the intersection of adversity healing and art and connected me with Ni2C, where I had the honor of working alongside the founder, Jen Andi. Jen's vision and dedication to the mission of Ni2C has been an inspiration throughout this creative journey. It is unconditionally fulfilling to be the workbook designer and see how it'll be used for future participants.

My sincere gratitude is extended to the Cal State Fullerton University Honors Program for fostering an atmosphere that inspired me to venture beyond my comfort zone. The development of this project has been greatly aided by the resources and assistance offered by the Honors Program's faculty. This program has sparked my curiosity and allowed me to learn more about the subject that I am most passionate about.

My deepest appreciation goes to my mom, whose resilience and commitment to Orange County's mental health workforce inspired me to join the field. As a parent partner providing resources for Western Youth Services in Anaheim, she had been an essential light for parents motivated to build resilience . Her role as a facilitator for ACEs under the previous California Surgeon General has encouraged me to channel our shared passion for serving the community.

This project has been a journey of self-discovery, expanding my knowledge not only on the neuroscience behind trauma and brain development but also on the insightful impact of resilience and community support.

Thank you to all who's been a part of this journey.

Abstract

Over two thirds of children have experienced at least one traumatic event by the age of 16. (Samhsa, 2022) In order to prevent future childhood adversities, the impacts must be addressed. This project traces toxic stress' historical exploration leading to the crucial Adverse Childhood Experiences (ACE) study conducted by Kaiser Permanente and the CDC in the 1990s. The propelled understanding of the profound connection between childhood trauma and adult health conditions teaches the population to be mindful of toxic stress and how it can negatively impact development. The ACEs Study's contributions sparked opportunities for mental health programs to offer life-changing services. Collaborating with mental health professionals from NI2C, a nonprofit dedicated to integral coaching and trauma-informed programs, the project focuses on designing an original curriculum workbook. This workbook project explores resilient methods to heal trauma of clients from different locations around the world from NI2C's R.E.P.A.I.R program. The material is to provide healing practices to participants developing reflection prompts for coaching sessions. Combining psychological principles with artistic expression, the workbook was inspired from the 60-page curriculum used in their pilot program that aims to inspire resilience. Utilizing design, evidence-based insights on interpersonal trauma, and somatic grounding techniques, the workbook will be used for future cohorts.

Keywords: Trauma, ACE's study, non-profit, Art

Introduction – History of Toxic Stress

Trauma has been investigated since the 19th century, giving researchers the opportunity to explore the impact of toxic stress. Medical professors intended to identify the underlying causes of the illnesses of their time. French physician, Jean Martin Charcot spent his career researching the relationship between trauma and mental illness. (Taylor & Francis, 2019) Psychological studies like Charcot's work have been conducted to identify the root of social and behavioral problems around the world. In the 1990's, Kaiser Permanente and the CDC conducted the Adverse Childhood Experiences study for over two years to find the connection between trauma and health conditions in adults. The investigation intended to raise the importance of healthy childhoods to lower the risks of health problems, substance abuse and incarceration.

Trauma is identified as an unsettling emotional response to a distressing experience that alters an individual's perception of life. Trauma has the ability to rewire our brain. Functions like memory and responses to situation are disrupted putting our body in sympathetic state. Sympathetic state is activated keeping individual's brain on fight or flight. (Cleveland Clinic, 2023) Our amygdala, the part of our brain in charge of emotional processing becomes overactive activating this state during life situations and obstacles. The brain's prefrontal cortex is unable to properly regulate fear and other emotions. Stress on the mind and body leads to health issues if left unaddressed. (Taylor Leamey, 2022).

The economic cost of ACEs, substance abuse, and violence costs the United States one trillion dollars annually. (CDC-Kaiser, 2021) Survivors of child trauma are at higher risks of behavior problems and mental illness in adulthood. As our brain develops, our nervous system builds connections based on previous experiences that guide us through life's everyday events keeping control of our body's activities. It allows adults to process stress and problem solve more effectively, but this is changed when trauma is involved. Brain development is disrupted when youth experiences adversities. Experiencing these situations, overwhelms the stress hormones preventing the nervous system from regulating properly. Cognitive development may be jeopardize affecting memory, concentrate, and most importantly executive function. (Walden University, 2021). Although traumatic experiences cannot be undone, there are resources available to learn about our nervous system to promote beneficial connections.

Project Aim:

Trauma may be irreversible, but there are paths towards healing that can alter our brain's connections. These mindset changes can provide a different perspective on what has happened by focusing on growth for the future. Providing individuals with mindfulness practices can be a

powerful tool to build resilience. I collaborated with mental health professionals and the founder of Ni2C, a nonprofit organization dedicated to integral coaching and providing trauma informed programs, to design their program's curriculum workbook. The goal of this project is to design an original workbook that not only coaches but inspires participants to build resilience. The R.E.P.A.I.R program consisted of 13 weeks of classes and coaching sessions to help repair trauma wounds. By adding artistic design and evidence-based insights on interpersonal trauma, the workbook gears participants towards healing and strength with somatic grounding techniques. Somatic practices focus on the mind-body connection, helping individuals regulate their nervous system, manage stress, and cultivate a sense of safety. (Ni2C 2023) As a previous participant and observer of the program's pilot, I used my creative ability to transform a 60-page curriculum into an imaginative workbook.

The purpose of this project is not only to create a visually appealing workbook but also to contribute to the broader understanding and support system for individuals who have experienced trauma, ultimately promoting somatic healing of the mind, body, and soul. By intertwining the disciplines of psychology and art, this workbook project serves as an artistic extension of the ACE study, aiming to spotlight the critical importance of childhood trauma prevention and resiliency.

Beginning in March 2023, the founder of Ni2C and I researched the most effective ways to provide somatic practices for participants in a virtual course. We addressed the lack of diversity in the original ACE study by evaluating program feedback from participants around the world. Starting in June 2023, the program held their 13-week course. Using the feedback from participants, I was given the opportunity to design a curriculum workbook that participants would utilize during their sessions. My purpose was to bring an artistic touch to the program

using my understanding of psychological principles. With my undergraduate research focused on the impacts of ACEs, I was equipped to create foundational content for the workbook with the information provided in the curriculum documents. This fusion of research and artistic expression seeks to evoke emotional responses through illustrations, coaching, and journal-like reflection prompts.

Literature Review:

When we are brought into this world, our first experiences come from relationships with another human. For those that go through adverse childhood experiences, they are at higher risk of developing mental illnesses that hinder their daily lives. (Harris 2021) It leads to higher physical problems, behavioral issues, and potential substance abuse. What we endure during our early years will affect us for the rest of our lives. Whether the disruption occurs in the home or outside of the home, it influences our relationships and interactions throughout our lifetime. Long-term repercussions are consequences of toxic stress that have gone unaddressed. When traumatized children grow up, they are overwhelmed by guilt making them believe they're unworthy. (Newport Institute, 2022)

In our early childhood years, we go through the process of arborization. (American Psychological Association 2022). This is when our brains store information of our surroundings. What we experience, whether it's healthy or unhealthy, and forms linkages in our brain and sticks around until children hit puberty. During puberty, the Pruning process begins which refers to the withdrawal of connections formed in the early years. If experiences rarely occur, these experiences will release during Pruning. Synaptic pruning is the brain's way of discarding linkages in the brain that are needless. (Healthline 2018) From the ages of 2 to 10, these connections decline severely. In other words, what children go through the most will remain in

the nervous system, stored in their bodies. Which they'll carry for the rest of their lives, but if they're neglected in certain areas it will fade during their development. Neuroscience has been used to understand how the brain stores and reacts to trauma. Our nervous system orchestrates our perception of the world and what we experience the most leads to connections between nerve cells. (Brain Facts 2018) It's so powerful that it takes in the world we live in and develops our understanding. Every moment, our neurons use our brain's processed information to adapt and is essentially what allows us to survive. The science behind the development of the human brain can help researchers understand why receiving proper childhood care is essential to avoid negative health and social behavior.

The National Child Traumatic Stress Network claims, "child traumatic stressors occur when children and adolescents are exposed to traumatic events or traumatic situations that are overwhelm their ability to cope." This statement sheds light on how lack of resilience and support effects their perception of life. Children exposed to stressors are likely to resort to flight, fight or freeze responses rather than learning healthy communication and problem-solving skills.

ACEs Study:

The ACE study conducted by Kaiser Permanente and the CDC in the 1990's purpose was to raise the importance of healthy childhood experiences and promote adversity prevention in hopes of lowering health issues. From 1995 to 1997, Kaiser Permanente and CDC led an investigation, analyzing how abuse, neglect, and household challenges influences upcoming adults' health. Dr. Rob Anda and Dr. Vincent Felitti are the co-principal investigators. (ACE Interface 2014) Their investigation was to study childhood abuse as the root of society's issues. By tracking the effects of trauma throughout a person's life, they managed to find adverse childhood experiences as part of the public health issue. Taking place in San Diego, California,

17,000 participants were evaluated. (CDC-Kaiser 2021) These participants were surveyed and shared their childhood experiences with family dysfunction, neglect, maltreatment, and their health status. Their goal was to link the connection between these adversities and the problems that come with it.

The ACE study contains ten experiences that if a child is exposed to, it deepens the risk of developing mental and physical health problems. These factors are measured between the ages of 0-18 years old. The questionnaire is based on how many the participant has experienced out of ten. (CDC-Kaiser 1995) The measures used by the CDC and Kaiser Permanente are Physical abuse, sexual abuse, emotional abuse, physical neglect, emotional neglect, domestic violence, household substance abuse, household mental illness, parental separation, divorce, or death, Incarcerated household member.

Researchers had multiple variables when conducting the study. Considering age, ethnicity, sex, and education level, the participants were asked which adversities they've faced. Men and women's scores were recorded and presented as percentages. Out of the 17,000, 36.1% scored 0. The study's participants were predominately white, middle to upper class which doesn't accurately account for majority of communities. The factors measured mainly focused on household dysfunction. The survey demographic, despite being a large sample does not include more than 12 percent of a non-white race. This called for the expansion of the study to recognize that childhood experiences are found among all populations.

The Philadelphia Ace Project introduced bullying, financial disparity, community violence, racism, foster care, natural disasters, and neighborhood safety as factors of childhood trauma. (Philadelphia ACE project 2013) These indicators brought a different perspective of what is considered trauma. Growing up, children begin to explore the world and learn about

society. Eventually children will encounter or witness factors like bullying and racism. This is just as impactful as neglect in the household. With a sample demographic different from the original, the findings showed that stressors from living in an urban area are related to overall ACE scores.

Participants consisted of inner-city youth. The Philadelphia ACE project found that 83.2 percent of their sample had at least one ACE. 40% of Philadelphians experienced 4 or more expanded ACE factors. Almost 66 percent of these participants have had at least one ACE, while about 20 percent have experienced three or more. The more ACES a child experiences, the chances of negative outcomes are higher. (Expanded Aces Study 2020). This project backs up the necessity for diversity in trauma research as intersectionality plays a huge factor. The importance of expanding the study is to get more accurate scores in order to serve the underserved.

The difference in demographics between the original and extended study demonstrates that findings on one group doesn't account for all races, classes, and genders. The original was made up of 74.8% white participants, compared to 44.1% in the Philadelphia sample. Researchers' choice of sampling reflected the Philadelphia resident's race population. Black participants in the original study made up only 4.6% jumping to 42.5% in the expanded study. It's important to acknowledge the social and economic upbringings of each group in America, to recognize that some populations may have higher ACE score. (RWJF 2019) The executive summary mentions the need for services that address the unique environmental stressors of each community.

After analyzing both studies, Childhood trauma doesn't always develop from home; children can experience toxic stress away from their guardians. This is extremely vital in understanding as traumatic experiences outside the home may go unaddressed. Outside factors besides household

disfunctions are just as capable of negatively impacting a child's development. All communities have different values and must be evaluated individually to give the proper support and resilience encouragement.

Neuroscience Connection:

With mental health not receiving as much attention as physical health care, this leaves a gap in potentially connecting a patient's health to their past trauma. (Healio, 2016) 56% of parents claimed their family's pediatrician never brings up mental health concerns, while 22% claim their doctor does check up on their mental health. This is a concern since pediatricians are not adequately trained in mental health. This leads to medical providers sending their patients to mental health services which is an issue for families in financial despair. (U.S. News Health, 2008)

Our former Surgeon General of California, Nadine Burke Harris used her field to find connections between her patients' health and traumatic stressors. (TED 2015) As a pediatrician and founder of Center for Youth Wellness, she's dedicated her career to studying the connection of physical and mental health. After treating children in a low-income neighborhood of San Francisco, she noticed a trend of children who've experienced trauma with poor health. The lack of training in the medical field inspired her to spread its impact. Dr. Harris stated that those exposed to trauma are at a risk of heart and lung cancer lowering life expectancy by 20 years. (Burke Foundation, n.d.) Dedicated to her passion, she's been an advocate for children's wellbeing and empowering other medical institutions to account ACES while discussing the health of their patients.

Children with higher ACES score are more likely to fall into substance abuse. Unsupported adolescence may turn to substances as a way to cope with their stressors. Often

where there is no safe place to communicate or problem-solve, fleeing to drugs and alcohol works as a temporary yet harmful escape. Those who have experienced household adversities were 30 percent more likely to develop alcoholism compared to the average population. (Baylor 2019) A study screening recovery patients, supports the claim of adversities being linked to substance abuse. 82.8% reported six or more adversities and all participants had at least one. (National Library of Medicine 2018)

With this in mind, these behaviors increase the risk of other physical health issues. They're at higher risk of depression, diabetes, cancer, asthma, and heart disease. (CDC 2019) There is an increased risk of type 2 diabetes by 32 percent compared to patients with no ACES. (Jama Pediatrics 2018) With the connection between childhood development and health, institutions should implement training of childhood trauma and its relationship to health status. The medical field must recognize that mental and physical health are connected.

Building Resilience

Adversity prevention is essential to live a healthy life. While wanting to uplift communities, it's vital to stay mindful of different cultures Just because one resource helps one community, doesn't ensure that it is beneficial for another. From generations to another, history of experiences including historic trauma, slavery or injustice are passed down. In order to help aid communities, providers must recognize what is important to different groups. Creating a nurturing environment for families can motivate the youth to reach their ambitions. The CDC published strategies to strengthen the support of families in need. By providing economic support to have financial security, this can relieve some stressors. Also included are promoting skill learning, healthy activities, and public education campaigns. (CDC Fast Facts 2022) Families in

high performing neighborhoods are at a lower risk of adverse childhood experiences. Nourishing a community is essential is encouraging resiliency.

As there are different mental health resources available, it is not accessible for all. Wellness doesn't need to be expensive or out of reach. One universal method that requires no tools is mindfulness. It is the ability to be aware of surroundings and not allowing situations to become overwhelming. (Mindful, 2022) This technique involves coming down to our breathing. When we are unable to resort to healthy coping activities, our breath is one thing we can control. Being able to remain calm with yourself as your only resource, helps handle uneasy emotions.

Even our surroundings can become coping strategies. For example, art is known for being therapeutic. Several studies have confirmed that art therapy is highly effective in treating mental disorders like depression, anxiety, and phobias. Art is known for its ability to express emotions without verbal words. (rtor.org, 2018) Art Therapy is defined as art in a therapeutic context meant to release emotions. Its benefits include self-discovery, emotional release, and stress relief. Expressive art therapy for children inspires creativity and sense of calmness. By putting their emotions into an artistic piece, it lowers the chance of resorting to unhealthy coping skills. (Georgetown, 2016) Kids with mental and behavioral health conditions are able to use art as a different way of communication. Whether it is performing or visual arts, expressive arts positively impact development.

Overall, the arts are essential in building resilience and embracing individual identities. Josephine Ilarraza, the school social worker at P.S 54, Bronx, New York was inspired to teach students about healthy coping mechanisms. Using the Champion Creatively Alive Children grant, she designed the creative coping skills program. (Naesp, 2021) Students created journals, stress balls and paintings. These children used these skills at home and reminded peers about

being calm. The program inspired Marybelle Ferreira, the school's principal to incorporate the curriculum in the parent's book club. Parents who remained silent about their adversities due to language barriers still found comfort in telling their stories through art.

This creative coping mechanism communicates in ways that are not accessible through other disciplines, but unfortunately it is understudied. (Malchiodi, 2013) Verbally expressing feelings is not for everyone. Some may feel uncomfortable about opening up, which is why it's important to have different outlets for healing. Expression through art challenges tradition treatment by sparking creativity and resiliency. Art is imitation and representation of outer existence. (Philosophy of Art, 1999) It is subjective and can represent endless ideas. The incorporation of art in the mental health field opens the door to new forms of communication and sharing.

NI2C's values

There are different programs that serve communities who have experienced adversities. Nested Integral Coaching Constellation is a non-profit that strives to support communities through trauma-informed resources. The non-profit highlights six pillars that the program aims to build client's competencies in. These objectives are introduced each week and participants gain an understanding of their nervous system and inner emotions that may be unaware of. These concepts were our inspiration for the entire design process. The terms are defined based on the program's mission.

Resilience

Co-regulation, self-regulation, stress response.

Through a progressive collection of exercises, participants will gain the ability to recognize the current state of their autonomic nervous system, as well as the ability to return home to themselves to a state of calm and security after experiences of overwhelm, anxiety, triggers, or escalated energy.

Embodiment

Grounding, and somatic awareness.

Participants will gain understanding of their inner felt experience through a curated handful of practices designed to connect to the wisdom of their bodies, and to utilize that connection for healing.

Perspective

Opening for new possibilities.

We will engage in a practice to learn to shift our perspective to embody new opportunities and possibilities for life.

Awareness

Self-observation and reflection.

Through a series of guided prompts and exercises, we will play with noticing how our experience shifts when we are aware of how we focus our attention, how we relate to awareness, and where we locate our "self" in the experience.

Integration

Living from our wholeness.

Through a guided exploration, participants will sense into different parts of themselves and learn to reclaim the parts they have previously disconnected from. The result of ongoing practice in this area is a feeling that the life we are living is more whole and complete.

Responsiveness

Appropriately generate what is needed for ourselves, others, and the situation.

Participants will engage exercises designed to support building the skill of attuning to ourselves, others, and the space between. We will also try on a stance or attitude that allows our natural response to be appropriately attuned to providing what is needed.

Logo Design and Themes:

Ni2C is a startup non-profit and connected with me to originally to design art for their website. I created their logo. This was the first project giving me creative freedom to design something that resembled community and resilience. Working through drafts, it was vital to design a logo that resonated with healing and personal growth. It played a pivotal role in my design choices and themes for the workbook as we went for a nature theme. All artwork from that point forward incorporated earthy elements.

I chose green tones as the main design color to resemble growth and renewal. The other reoccurring colors were brown, blue, and neutral tones. Color symbolism is tied to the subconscious and can promote an emotional response. (Lauren David, 2023) This was an important factor for me in the beginning process My goal was to create an earth palate that matched each scenery background photo. The front cover, opening page, survey, coaching notes, and back cover combine the main palate colors. Light colors were used in the opening page to represent a brighter future ahead.

Front Cover

Back Cover

Front Cover

Back Cover

R.E.P.A.I.R. Program

Starting April 2024; and September 2024
 Receive one-on-one coaching, find a community of support, and learn to integrate the following competencies that are essential to recovering from trauma: Resilience. Embodiment. Perspective. Awareness. Integration. Responsiveness.

R.E.P.A.I.R.

Scarlett R 2024

Jen asked me to create an artwork that represented a calm state of mind to use as symbolism of mindfulness. We went through numerous rounds of brainstorm and editing to find the right composition that complimented the theme.

The artwork above was chosen as the final website cover.

Adding artwork to their program gives viewers the opportunity to connect with their emotions. A study from University of Turku found that artwork is associated with positive emotions. The composition reinforces the

connection between mindfulness and the natural world. The body releases sensations as a reaction to the artwork. (University of Turku, 2023) The goal was for potential clients to feel calm and grounded as a way to encourage participation in the program. This artwork aligns the principles of a calm state of mind, growth and being present in the moment. The nature background and meditation pose is to convey balance within our environment. The flowers represent the rebirth of mindset after practicing mindfulness.

Illustrations

The R.E.P.A.I.R program stands for Resilience, Embodiment, Perspective, Awareness, Integration and Responsiveness. Similar to the cover art, each artwork went through multiple drafts. The final pieces have been added into the workbook to give an idea to participants about what the meaning of each value is. During the week of Perspective, participants take on three poses to see what is possible from each perspective. These practices gave participants the opportunity to step away from their own body and see from a different perspective. Artwork was used throughout the workbook to emphasize the material.

Learning Objectives

Resilience Co-Regulation & self-regulation, working with nervous system to recognize and shift states.	Embodiment Grounding & somatic awareness.	Perspective Opening for new possibilities.
Awareness Self-observation, mindfulness, & reflection.	Integration Living from our wholeness.	Responsiveness Appropriately generate what is needed for ourselves, others, and the situation.

v

Introduction to Perspective

Sensing inward, how am I in this moment?

Physically:

Emotionally:

Mentally:

Becoming Unstuck

When we find ourselves stuck in a seemingly choiceless situation, or when we find ourselves in a rut repeating the same behavior like a broken record, working with shifting our perspective may illuminate possibilities that previously seemed out of reach.

This cognitive approach is a useful exercise for thinking outside of the box to find new ways of seeing, thinking, and responding that are outside of our habitual ways of being.

This week, we'll be physically moving our bodies, and observing what feels possible from different shapes. As we show up with a different purpose or intention, different possibilities open for us. This tells us that how we show up impacts our experience. We will take on a few different shapes to play with this idea.

Archer	Nurturer	Explorer

52

Main pieces, filler artwork, and drafts

The Completed Workbook

After 200 hours, the workbook is finally completed and ready to be printed and shipped to upcoming participants. The program consisted of 13 weeks of material that was taught to participants in somatic ways. This included breathing exercises, yoga, dancing, music, and other body techniques. The curriculum introduces participants to body-based therapy which is used to relieve trauma survivors. The body and brain goes through rewiring which leaves subconscious thoughts that are inaccessible through cognitive approaches. Trauma can leave imbedded beliefs that negatively impact an individual's perception of life. (Integrative Psychotherapy, 2023) The purpose of translating the curriculum into a workbook was for participants to be able to engage in mindful practices on their own time. It gives them the opportunity to reflect on their process and discover their inner self.

The board of directors and coaches at Ni2C conducted several meetings reviewing the material in the workbook draft. Their input was crucial in ensure that the language was inclusive and suitable to evoke the appropriate emotions in participants. The collaborative review process also led to the addition of new materials, which improved the workbook's overall flow. The valuable advice from the board of directors recommended a page with information to resources like the ACEs survey.

Student Resources
www.ni2c.org/student-resources

- Guided Practices & Exercises**
 - Meditations
 - Somatic Practices
 - Visualizations
 - Slideshows
 - Worksheets
- Inspiration Corner**
 - Poetry
 - Songs
 - Quotes
 - Art
 - Testimonials
- Ways to Stay Connected**
 - LinkedIn REPAIR Alumni Group
 - Facebook REPAIR Alumni Group
 - Subscribe to newsletter
 - Give feedback
- Beyond REPAIR**
 - Research
 - Recommended reading
 - Additional courses
 - Audio/video library
 - ACEs survey

Reflection: The Fulfilling Journey of Contributing to Resilience

The ACEs literature research for my SHP is directly related to the Ni2C workbook content. The REPAIR Program, which focuses on individuals affected by interpersonal trauma, is consistent with the findings of the ACEs study by highlighting the long-lasting consequences of childhood trauma. Research findings are translated into useful resources in the program's workbook. It tackles the burdens that people might bear as a result of trauma, reinforcing the program's emphasis on recovery and wholeness. The program's individual coaching sessions, group practices, and weekly Zoom sessions are in line with the literature's emphasis on individualized interventions and supportive environments. (NI2C, 2023)

As I reflect on this year-long project, I learned that barriers were not to hinder me, but to overcome with strength. I saw my design process advance with each page and each critique were steppingstones that led to improvement of the final draft. My satisfaction derived from comes not only from the opportunity to utilize my talents but, more importantly, from the knowledge that the workbook will play a vital role in supporting individuals on their path to resilience.

. By channeling my artistic gifts into this meaningful cause, I've found a way to contribute to a nonprofit organization dedicated to trauma-informed programming and holistic coaching. Designing the Ni2C workbook has been an immensely rewarding journey, perfectly aligning with my commitment to giving back to the community This experience has improved my design abilities, but it has also given me a strong sense of purpose to use my creativity to improve the lives of others. This experience has been a fulfilling intersection of passion, creativity, and the chance to make a positive impact in the lives of those who can benefit most from it.

Conclusion

Childhood trauma plays a huge role in society's issues. The ACE study conducted by Kaiser and the CDC demonstrates the importance of healthy childhoods. Without proper care during our early years, it can lead to health risks in adulthood. Our brain is constantly making connections, taking in our surroundings to help improve decision making. Exposure to toxic stress jeopardizes the healthy development of our brain, potentially putting individuals at risk of health complications. The study continues to expand taking into consideration of other unhealthy factors that change the signals to the brain. The Philadelphia ACE project analyzed the impact of factors like racism and socioeconomic status being added to the original 10 measurements. The original and extended study were considered during this project by creating a workbook that was inclusive of all especially as the program supports clients around the world. Being mindful of cultural differences extend researcher's knowledge on the relationship of health and trauma experiences. Advocacy for medical institutions to incorporate ACES training into their field is crucial to make a difference in individuals' lives.

In wrapping up this project, the result is an original workbook designed not just for coaching but to ignite inspiration in participants, propelling them toward resilience. My creative efforts transformed a conventional 60-page curriculum into an imaginative workbook. Aligned with the R.E.P.A.I.R program's 13-week approach to healing trauma wounds, the workbook emerges as an influential tool for participants. Infused with artistic design and grounded in evidence-based insights on interpersonal trauma, it purposefully steers participants toward strength and healing, engaging in somatic grounding techniques that emphasize the vital mind-body connection. This interdisciplinary mission, weaving together psychology and art, holds the workbook as an artistic extension of the ACE study.

References

- Sütterlin, N. (2019). "History of Trauma Theory". In: Colin Davis and Hanna Meretoja (eds.): Routledge Companion to Literature and Trauma. Abingdon: Taylor & Francis, 2020. *Harvard*.
https://www.academia.edu/38084072/_History_of_Trauma_Theory_In_Colin_Davis_and_Hanna_Meretoja_edrs_Routledge_Companion_to_Literature_and_Trauma_Abingdon_Taylor_and_Fran_cis_2020
- Professional, C. C. M. (n.d.). Sympathetic Nervous System (SNS). Cleveland Clinic.
<https://my.clevelandclinic.org/health/body/23262-sympathetic-nervous-system-sns-fight-or-flight>
- Leamey, T., & Sun, V. (2022, November 5). Both your body and brain are different after trauma. What to know. *CNET*. <https://www.cnet.com/health/mental/how-trauma-makes-neurobiological-changes-to-your-brain-and-body/>
- mindbodygreen. (2023, April 27). *Is your favorite color green? Here's what it symbolizes & represents*. Mindbodygreen. <https://www.mindbodygreen.com/articles/green-symbolism>
- Neuroscience News. (2023, March 27). *Art evokes feelings in the body*.
<https://neurosciencenews.com/art-body-emotion-22883/#:~:text=%E2%80%9CThe%20bodily%20sensations%20evoked%20by,the%20Universit y%20of%20Turku%2C%20Finland.>
- Goldstein, E. (2023, November 8). *10 Somatic interventions explained — Integrative Psychotherapy Mental Health blog*. Integrative Psychotherapy & Trauma Treatment.
<https://integrativepsych.co/new-blog/somatic-therapy-explained-methods>
- Walden University. (2021, March 25). *How Trauma Affects Child Development and Behavior: What Childhood Educators Need to Know*. <https://www.waldenu.edu/online-masters->

[programs/ms-in-early-childhood-studies/resource/how-trauma-affects-child-development-and-behavior](#)

EXPANDED-ACES-STUDY. (2020, June 19).

<https://cornerstonesofcare.org/Blog/2020/06/19/An-Expanded-Look-at-Adverse-Childhood-Experience-ACE-Studies>

Newport Institute Staff. (2022, September 26). *4 Ways Childhood Trauma Impacts Young Adult Thriving*. Newport Institute. <https://www.newportinstitute.com/resources/treatment/childhood-trauma/>

Most pediatricians do not use mental health clinicians to co-manage patients. (2016, May 1).

<https://www.healio.com/news/pediatrics/20160501/most-pediatricians-do-not-use-mental-health-clinicians-to-co-manage-patients>

Walsh, C. (2019j, April 2). *Harvard researcher on psychology of art*. Harvard Gazette.

<https://news.harvard.edu/gazette/story/2019/04/harvard-researcher-on-psychology-of-art/>

History of Trauma Theory. (2020). Sagepub. https://www.sagepub.com/sites/default/files/upm-binaries/40688_1.pdf

“The Trauma-Informed Network of Care Roadmap: A Guide for Strengthening Community Relationships.” ACEs Aware, 2 July 2021, www.acesaware.org/events/the-trauma-informed-network-of-care-roadmap-a-guide-for-strengthening-community-relationships.

“What Is Child Trauma?” *Center for Child Trauma Assessment and Service Planning*, 22 June 2020, cctasi.northwestern.edu/child-trauma

Ace Interface: Robert Anda. www.aceinterface.com/Robert_Anda.html

Cafasso, Jacquelyn. “What Is Synaptic Pruning?” *Healthline*, 18 Sept. 2018, www.healthline.com/health/synaptic-pruning

APA Dictionary of Psychology. dictionary.apa.org/arborization

Top 10 ACEs – Resilient Child Fund. www.resilientchildfund.org/top-10-aces

“What Is Child Trauma?” *Center for Child Trauma Assessment and Service Planning*, 22 June 2020, cctasi.northwestern.edu/child-trauma.

Pediatricians Don’t Routinely Ask About Mental Health. (2008). U.S News Health.

<https://health.usnews.com/health-news/blogs/on-parenting/2008/12/15/pediatricians-dont-routinely-ask-about-mental-health>

Mindful Communications & Such PBC. (2022, November 28). *Getting Started with ness*.

Mindful. <https://www.mindful.org/meditation/mindfulness-getting-started/>

Adverse Childhood Experiences | National Human Trafficking Training and Technical

Assistance Center. nhttac.acf.hhs.gov/soar/eguide/stop/adverse_childhood_experiences

About the CDC-Kaiser ACE Study | Violence Prevention | Injury Center | CDC.

www.cdc.gov/violenceprevention/aces/about.html

History | Philadelphia ACES. www.philadelphiaaces.org/about-us/history

How Neurons Communicate. www.brainfacts.org/core-concepts/how-neurons-communicate

“Findings From the Philadelphia Urban ACE Survey.” *RWJF*, 17 Dec. 2019,

www.rwjf.org/en/library/research/2013/09/findings-from-the-philadelphia-urban-ace-survey.html

Philosophy of art | Definition, Theories, History, & Facts. (1999, July 26). Encyclopedia

Britannica. <https://www.britannica.com/topic/philosophy-of-art/Art-as-expression>

Harris, Nadine Burke. “Nadine Burke Harris | Speaker | TED.” *TED Talks*,

www.ted.com/speakers/nadine_burke_harris_1

“The Link Between Adverse Childhood Experiences and Later-Life Health | Online Graduate Programs | Baylor.” *BAY-UMT*, 23 Mar. 2021, onlinegrad.baylor.edu/resources/adverse-childhood-experiences-health

Malchiodi, C. A. (2020). *Trauma and Expressive Arts Therapy: Brain, Body and Imagination in the Healing Process*. New York: Guilford Press.

Chandler GE, Kalmakis KA, Murtha T. Screening Adults With Substance Use Disorder for Adverse Childhood Experiences. *J Addict Nurs*. 2018
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/30180003/>

Friedman, J. (2019, October 1). *Use Art to Learn Empathy and Create Social Change*. Doing Good Together™. <https://www.doinggoodtogether.org/dgt-newsletter/art-empathy-social-change>

Guest Author for www.rtor.org. (2020, July 29). *Creativity and Recovery: The Mental Health Benefits of Art Therapy*. Resources to Recover. <https://www.rtor.org/2018/07/10/benefits-of-art-therapy/>

Adverse childhood experiences and unhealthy lifestyles later in life: evidence from SHARE countries. (2022, August 24). SpringerLink. https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s11150-022-09612-y?error=cookies_not_supported&code=cd3ee6e5-9206-4243-9970-3b07e11da2bf

About the CDC-Kaiser ACE Study | Violence Prevention | Injury Center | CDC. (n.d.).
<https://www.cdc.gov/violenceprevention/aces/about.html>

Hoare, A. (2021, September 26). *Digital Illustration Styles*. The Illustrators.
<https://www.theillustrators.com.au/digital-illustration-styles>

Understanding Child Trauma. (2022, September 27). SAMHSA. <https://www.samhsa.gov/child-trauma/understanding-child-trauma>

5 Ways Childhood Trauma Affects Adulthood. (2022, April 12) Akua Mind Body
akuamindbody.com/5-ways-childhood-trauma-affects-adulthood

Benefits of Expressive Art Therapy for Children | Georgetown Behavioral. (n.d.).

<https://www.georgetownbehavioral.com/blog/expressive-art-therapy-for-children>

Naesp, N., & Staff, N. (2021, January 14). *Using the Arts to Address Adverse Childhood*

Experiences. NAESP. <https://www.naesp.org/resource/using-the-arts-to-address-adverse-childhood-experiences/>

Constellation, N. I. C. (n.d.). *Nested Integral Coaching Constellation.* Nested Integral Coaching

Constellation. <https://ni2c.org/>